

Transmission Zeros in In-line Filters by Using Source-to-Load Paths With Suppressed Spurious Frequencies

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Abstract — This paper presents a new class of in-line rectangular waveguide filters with source-to-load (S-L) coupling for generating transmission zeros (TZs). The easiest way to obtain a direct S-L coupling is to connect source and load by a secondary path realized with a waveguide section. However, in an in-line filters, source and load are in general distant, this resulting in a long waveguide section that generate spurious frequencies that degrade the filter performance. In this paper, an alternative method where the secondary path is realized by the cascade of cavities is introduced. Resonances generated by the cavities of the secondary path are then removed by exploiting the spurious self-suppression method. Cavities in secondary path can have a very small volume and their contribution to the filter Q-factor is extremely limited. This results in a secondary path that has a limited impact on the dimension of the whole filter. To validate the proposed method, a 4th order filter has been designed, fabricated, and measured.

Keywords — Source to load (S-L) coupling, secondary path, transmission zeros (TZs), waveguide filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Waveguide filters with high selectivity are required in modern communication system to meet the stringent requirement below and above the passband. Transmission zeros (TZs) in filters are important to meet such requirements and enhance the filter selectivity. Multiple techniques have been used so far to generate TZs in microwave filters [1]. The use of cross couplings between non-adjacent resonators allows for the realization of filter having responses with TZs. This is in general obtained by using folded structures [2]. Several synthesis techniques for filters with folded configuration are presented in [3], [4]. Waveguide filter with resonant S-L and bypass cross couplings is reported in [5]. However, for some applications, including satellite applications, in-line configuration filters are often preferred [6]. Some S-L coupling structures for microstrip technology are reported in [7], [8].

In this paper, a new in-line configuration of rectangular waveguide filter implementing S-L coupling to generate TZs is presented. The primary filter generating the passband consists in the cascading of classical rectangular waveguide cavities. S-L coupling is instead realized by using a secondary path consisting of two resonators of small volume ($h=5mm$) connecting input and output of the in-line rectangular waveguide filter. The proposed method exploits the recently proposed spurious self-suppression method [9], [10] for

eliminating the spurious frequencies generated by the secondary path. This allows for the creation of a secondary path where resonances are suppressed. Indeed, the main problem in creating a S-L coupling with an additional path in an in-line filter is that this results in a long path which create resonances that degrade the filter response. With the proposed method instead, we are able to transfer some power from the source to the load of the filter avoiding spurious resonances.

It is interesting to note that the additional losses introduced by secondary path does not contribute to the filter in-band losses. Hence the Q-factor of the filter is not degraded. This allows keeping the dimension of the secondary path very small, so that it does not significantly contribute to the overall filter dimensions. Fourth order filter using classical rectangular waveguide cavities is designed, fabricated and measured. Good agreement between simulation and measured results were achieved.

II. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT ANALYSIS

The proposed method is first analysed in terms of the equivalent circuit. Equivalent circuit is shown in Fig. 1, and it consists of resonators R1, R2, R3, R4 implementing the filter generating the passband at 10 GHz, and resonators R5 and R6 implementing the secondary path generating S-L coupling. Resonators in the secondary path resonates out of the filter band (11 GHz in the considered example). Fig. 2 shows the response of the equivalent circuit along with the normalized coupling values. In this case, the self-suppression method for the secondary path has not yet been applied. This results in a secondary path generating a spurious band at 11 GHz. In Fig. 2a all the couplings in the filter are inductive/positive including that in the secondary path. This leads to a response with no TZs.

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit of 4th order filter implementing S-L coupling using secondary path.

Fig. 2. (a) Response of equivalent circuit without TZs. Normalized coupling values are; $M_{s1}=0.85$, $M_{12}=0.6$, $M_{23}=0.46$, $M_{s5}=0.5$, $M_{s6}=0.5$. (b) Response of equivalent circuit with TZs. Normalized coupling values are; $M_{s1}=0.85$, $M_{12}=0.6$, $M_{23}=-0.46$, $M_{s5}=0.5$, $M_{s6}=0.5$.

In order to obtain TZs, one of the coupling signs either in the primary filter or in the secondary path must be changed. Fig. 2b shows what happens when the sign of coupling M_{23} is changed. As can be seen two TZs appear: one in the lower and the other in the upper stopband. The same result could have been obtained by changing the sign of any other coupling.

The last step consists in removing the spurious resonances generated by the secondary path. This can be done by using the recently proposed spurious self-suppression method [9], [10], which consist in minimizing only the central coupling value and maximizing all other couplings in the secondary path. Fig. 3 shows the response of the filter with TZs, and it also shows how to suppress the resonances generated by the secondary path. The coupling coefficients of the secondary path are $M_{s5}=M_{6L}$ and M_{s6} . Fig. 3 shows what happens to the spurious frequencies for different values of such couplings. In particular, when all the couplings are 0.5 (black curve) there is a wide spurious band at 11 GHz. If all couplings are instead reduced to 0.1 (red curve), the spurious frequency still reaches 0 dB and in addition the TZs goes far away from the filter band because the total power that bypasses the filter decreases. Blue curve shows instead what happens when the spurious suppression method is applied [9], [10] by minimizing M_{s6} and maximizing M_{s5} (M_{6L}). In this case, the spurious band is suppressed and TZs remain close to the filter passband.

Fig. 3. Four pole equivalent circuit response with TZs and suppressed resonances.

III. RECTANGULAR WAVEGUIDE FILTER DESIGN

The equivalent circuit analysis discussed above for S-L coupling and resonance suppression method is applied here to the design of a 4th order filter with in-line configuration.

A. Filter Design Without TZs

The first design shown in Fig. 4a implements the equivalent circuit of Fig. 2a. The response of the filter is shown in Fig. 4b. Filter band is centered at 9.6 GHz with a FBW of 3%. As expected, there are no TZs in the filter response, however the secondary path produces several spurious frequencies below and above the passband. More spurious frequencies than that of the equivalent circuit. This is because both TE_{102} and TE_{103} modes resonate in cavities R5 and R6 in the graph frequency. In particular, TE_{102} is responsible for the spurious frequency around 8.7 GHz, and TE_{103} for that around 10.5 GHz. In terms of equivalent circuit this correspond to an additional source to load path.

Fig. 4. 4th order filter without TZs. (a) 3d structure. (b) S parameters response.

B. Filter design with TZs

According to what is explained regarding Fig. 2b, in order to obtain visible TZs, it is necessary to change the sign of one coupling. This has been done by transforming the central inductive iris of the filter into a capacitive iris. Fig. 5a shows the 3d structure of the filter and its response is shown in Fig. 5b. TZs are located at 9.13GHz and 10.15GHz. An additional TZ is also present at 11.2GHz.

According to the spurious self-suppression procedure, the resonances generated by the secondary path can be easily suppressed by properly setting their coupling values. Fig. 6 shows the effect of the variation of coupling values in the secondary path. The central coupling value M_{56} of the secondary path has been minimized by reducing the width w_2 of the iris connecting resonators R5 and R6. The coupling M_{55} can be maximized by increasing the length l_1 of the iris that connects source S to resonator R5. Note that, when M_{56} is minimized by reducing w_2 , TZs moves away from the passband (red curve). However, when M_{55} is maximized by increasing the length of iris $l_1=3.5mm$ (blue curve), TZ get closer to the passband improving filter selectivity in lower stopband region. The spurious resonance below passband due to TE_{102} mode has been suppressed up to 40dB. While the spurious frequencies present above the passband due to TE_{103} mode has been suppressed up to 20dB.

Fig. 5. 4th order filter with TZs. (a) 3d structure. (b) S parameters response.

Fig. 6. Effect of minimizing and maximizing coupling to secondary path.

C. Control of TZs position

Fig. 6 shows that the selectivity of the response in the lower stopband is better than that in the upper stopband. However, location of the TZs can be easily controlled and filter selectivity can be improved in the upper stopband region by decreasing the resonance frequency of cavities in the secondary path. The resonance frequencies in the secondary path have been decreased by increasing the width w_g of resonators R5 and R6, and the effect can be seen in Fig. 7a. Note that, increasing w_g , the bandwidth of the parasitic band generated by the TE_{103} modes become narrower and the two TZs at the upper stopband become closer and approaches the filter band. Fig. 7b shows the final response of the filter. In the final response, rounded corner has been considered in order to facilitate the manufacturing process. Filter dimensions are: $w_g=31mm$, $w_l=22.86mm$, $w_2=3mm$, $l=4.7mm$, $l_1=3.5mm$, $l_g=53.2mm$, $h=5mm$.

Fig. 7. Effect of increasing the resonance frequency of secondary path. (b) Final filter response.

IV. MEASUREMENT OF THE PROPOSED 4TH ORDER FILTER

In order to validate the design, the 4th order filter prototype has been manufactured and measured. The photograph of the manufactured filter is shown in Fig. 8a. 3D printer Formlabs Form2 has been exploited to manufacture the proposed prototype. The filter was manufactured in two halves and assembled using screws in order to allow the metallization. Inside cavities edges has been rounded to facilitate the manufacturing of the prototype. In order to make metallization process easy, a height $h=5$ mm has been considered for the additional path, however much smaller height can be used with almost no effects on the filter Q-factor. Fig. 8b shows the comparison between simulated and measured results. Measured results show very good agreement with the simulations. The measured return loss is below -14.5dB, and it can be further improved by using tuning screws (in this prototype no tuning screws have been used). Measured insertion loss is about -1.2 dB at the mid band of the filter. The relatively low Q-factor 550 is not due to the presence of the secondary path, but it is due to the not effective metallization, as can be seen in Fig. 8a.

Fig. 8. (a) 3d printed photograph (b). Comparison between simulated and measured results.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new method implementing the S-L coupling for generating TZs in bandpass filter has been presented. S-L coupling is realized using an additional path consisting of two cavities with small height that resonates out of the filter band. The resonances generated by resonators of the secondary path have been suppressed by using a technique called spurious self-suppression method. The proposed approach has been applied to in-line rectangular waveguide filters. This method allows for achieving filter selectivity on either side of the passband and TZs position can be controlled by changing the resonance frequency of cavities in the secondary path. A 4th order filter centered at 9.6GHz with a FBW of 3%, has been designed and manufactured using 3d printing technology. Good agreement between simulation and measured results have been achieved.

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